

Clinical Study on the efficacy of Auriculotherapy in the treatment of Secondary Amenorrhea

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Abstract

Objective: The Clinical Study to determine the efficacy of Auriculotherapy in the treatment of Amenorrhea

Method: (1) Auriculotherapy treatment session was done with the frequency of once a month. (2) The selected auricular points are treated with dual vaccaria seeds. (3) The applied seeds are to be maintained by the patients for a period of one month. (4) The applied individual seeds are to be pressed (stimulated) manually three time a day, by the patients. (5) The applied seeds are to be protected from the soaking of the water.

Result: The subject cases were reviewed after 3 treatment sessions. Total 50/52 (96%) cases were benefited with the treatment. Follow-up could be obtained from most of the cases (45/52) for a minimum of 6 months after the treatment was over and all of them were symptom free i.e. continue with the regular menses. Out of this, 26 cases continued symptom free period for more than one year and all of them were symptom free i.e. continue with regular menses.

Conclusion: The data suggest that the Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory, long term effect in the treatment of secondary amenorrhea. After looking at the results of the above cases, the control study may help further to get more clarity on the subject.

Keywords

Amenorrhea, Auriculotherapy, TCM, Acupuncture

Introduction

The secondary amenorrhea refers to stoppage of menses for more than three months after the menarche is achieved.

Nowadays, this is a very common problem observed in young women due to the stress and change in life style including diet, exercise, sleep, & exposure to various chemical toxins in the environment.

This condition affects their learning, earning, reproduction and quality of life. When this condition is prolonged, it can cause depression.

Currently, no known easy therapy is available for treating Amenorrhea. With conventional medical treatment, which is usually based on hormone, has a drawback like side effects and recurrence after discontinuation.

This study was conducted in Treatment Camp organized in rural village area (440 km away from Mumbai). The treatment frequency was once in a month.

General medical conditions are treated in this treatment camp. Seeing the amazing response, the retrospective study was conducted of the cases of secondary amenorrhea, which is presented herewith.

The total 52 cases were studied.

The patients in this area do not have adequate financial resources for their treatment and/or investigations. As such the conventional diagnostic investigations such as blood/hormone report, USG were not available of the subject cases. However, the diagnosis as per TCM and Auriculotherapy were performed for all the cases.

The criteria for selection of the patients was as follows

- The patients had their menses after the menarche but their menses have ceased for over three months (this excludes the cases of physiological condition such as pregnant and breast feeding women)
- Age of the subject patients were up to 40 years

After getting astonishing results from Auriculotherapy, the patients were followed up after completion of 3 treatment sessions. Most of the patients were followed up for a period of minimum 6 months to 1 year, to ascertain the effect of the treatment.

Method

Auriculotherapy was selected as the treatment method for the cases for secondary amenorrhea since the Auriculotherapy has following salient features.

- Simple for application
- Cost effective
- No side effects
- Does not require frequent visits
- It regulates the functions

The diagnosis of the patients were performed as per TCM and Auriculotherapy postulate. The following procedure is followed and based on this basis the ear points were selected and applied.

Diagnosis

Inspection:

A pale or swollen area at Uterus point on ear. (Ref. Fig.1 Inspection of Auricle - Amenorrhea)

Palpation:

A pale pressing mark at Uterus point on ear when checked with diagnostic probe.

Electrical Detection:

Positive reactions found at Uterus, Ovary, Endocrine, Hypothalamus, and Pituitary Gland, when checked with Electrical Point Detector.

Fig.1: Inspection of Auricle - Amenorrhea

Fig.2: Selection of Points - Amenorrhea

Point Selection:

Main Points: Uterus, Ovary, Brain, Kidney, Liver, Endocrine, Spleen (Ref. Fig.2 Point Selection)

Treatment Protocol

1. Auriculotherapy treatment session was done with the frequency of once a month.
2. The selected auricular points are treated with dual vaccaria seeds.
3. The applied seeds are to be maintained by the patients for a period of one month. However, it was observed that the seeds are normally maintained for a period of 21 to 30 days after application.
4. The applied individual seeds are to be pressed (stimulated) manually three time a day, by the patients.
5. The applied seeds are to be protected from the soaking of the water.

The total cases registered were 52. Refer Table 1 for the differentiation of the cases based on the number of cycles of missed period.

Table 1: Differentiation based on the number of cycles of missed period

Total no. of cycles of missed period	Cases
3 cycles	27
6 cycles	20
12 cycles	5
Total	52

Result

The subject cases were reviewed after 3 treatment sessions and results are as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Results after 3 treatment sessions

Restored menstrual flow after	No. of Cases
1 treatment session	34
2 treatment sessions	11
3 treatment sessions	5

2 patients did not respond after 3 treatment sessions

Total 50/52 (96%) cases were benefited with the treatment.

Follow-up could be obtained from most of the cases (45/52) for a minimum of 6 months after the treatment was over and all of them were symptom free i.e. continue with the regular menses.

Out of this, 26 cases continued symptom free period for more than one year and all of them were symptom free i.e. continue with regular menses.

Discussion

In TCM, amenorrhea is due to a disorder of Qi and blood and is due to a dysfunction of the Zang-Fu organs, which may lead to impairment of the Chong and Ren Channels.

It can be classified into a deficient type and an excessive type.

The deficiency type is mostly caused by exhaustion of essence and blood in the liver and kidney or deficiency of Qi and blood;

The excess type is due to obstruction in the Chong and Ren Channels resulting from stagnation of Qi and blood or from stagnation of phlegm-dampness.

Point Selection:

Uterus, Ovary, Brain, Kidney, Liver, Endocrine, Spleen.

Purpose of Point Selection:

Uterus is selected as a corresponding point to regulate circulation of Qi and blood in the uterus.

Ovary, Brain, Endocrine: To regulate the function of the endocrine system and ovaries.

Liver, Kidney, Spleen: For amenorrhea due to deficiency of spleen-Qi or deficiency of the liver and kidney, these three points were selected to replenish Qi, nourish blood and tone the liver and kidney; for amenorrhea due to stagnation of Qi and blood, the point, Liver was used to regulate the flow of Qi and promote blood circulation to remove blood stasis.

Location of Points

Uterus: This point is located at the middle of the front edge of the depression in the Triangular Fossa.

Ovary: It is located at the outer edge of the lateral portion of the Intertragic Notch.

Brain: It is located at center of the upper half of the interior Antitragus.

Kidney: It is located at the lateral superior-interior corner of the Cymba Concha.

Liver: It is located in the lateral inferior area of the Cymba Concha.

Endocrine: It is located in the inferior portion of the Cavum Concha, 0.5 cm down from the Intertragic Notch.

Spleen: It is located in Cavum Concha at the midpoint of a line from the Stomach to the Helix Notch (between Antihelix and Antitragus).

Conclusions

The data suggest that the Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory, long term effect in the treatment of secondary amenorrhea.

After looking at the results of the above cases, the control study may help further to get more clarity on the subject.

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